

Formative Evaluation of the Implementation Semai Benih Bangsa (SBB) from Indonesia Heritage Foundation (IHF) at SBB Tapos

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ABSTRACT: This study tries to look the implementation of the Semai Benih Bangsa program conducted by the Indonesia Heritage Foundation. This study is a formative evaluation research with an emphasis on process studies with the scope of evaluation of inputs and activities. This study was taken with qualitative approach involving a number of informants from internal organizations, stakeholders and beneficiaries. From the results of the study, it was found that, in the input aspect consisting of beneficiaries, SBB facilities, IHF management human resources, SBB teacher human resources, funds and networks have successfully run according to the setting up. However, in the aspect of activities, there are several activities that have not been carried out according to the setting up; PHBK model training and SBB school meetings. Meanwhile, monitoring activities are in accordance with the program settings. This study also discusses the obstacles encountered in implementing program and look efforts from foundation in dealing with these obstacles.

KEYWORDS -Human Service Organizations, Formative Evaluation; Character building; Character Based Holistic Education

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is a large country with a population of around 268 million people consisting of multicultural and divided into archipelagic areas. According to data from the Central Statistics Agency, the total population of Indonesia in 2020 amounted to 270.20 million people. The percentage of population composition in the age group of 15-64 years (productive age) is the largest, namely 70.72%. The population with the age group of 0-14 years is about 23.33% of the total population and the age group of more than 65 years (age that is already unproductive) amounts to 5.95% of the total population. In other words, Indonesia is currently enjoying a period of demographic bonus because the number of productive age people is more than the unproductive age. The magnitude of this productive age figure can be said to be a demographic bonus. This is referred to as a window of opportunity because the condition is only in the form of potential, whose actualization depends on many factors and sectors that must of course be maximized. According to the Directorate General of Public Information and Communication, there are at least five key factors as an effort to maximize the window of opportunity. These factors, namely quality human resources (HR), human resources are absorbed in the job market, savings are available at the household level, continue to intensify the family planning program/Birth Control and women in the job market. With the strengthening of these five factors, Indonesia will achieve maximum time in the face of demographic bonuses, which will certainly have an impact on development in all aspects. Besides the window of opportunity, unfortunately the demographic bonus not only presents a great positive opportunity, but also has a negative impact, if the existing human resources do not have qualified quality.

The concept of human resources according to Mullins (2005) is actually a planning, implementation and maintenance strategy that aims to manage humans, in order to have maximum business performance, including development policies and processes to support strategies. Singodimedjo (2000) suggests that human resource development is the process of preparing individuals to assume different or higher responsibilities within the organization, usually related to improving intellectual ability to carry out better tasks.

Indonesia has long been committed to advancing human resources, one of which is education. The purpose of improving quality human resources is stated in Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, article 3 explains that the essence of the purpose of education is to develop abilities and form the character and character of a dignified nation in order to educate the nation's life, aiming to develop the potential of students to become faithful human beings and devotion to God Almighty, have noble character, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, become a democratic and responsible citizen.

The development of quality human resources can be seen from the Human Development Index of the Republic of Indonesia. Based on data from the Central Statistics Agency 2020, in this decade, human development in Indonesia continues to increase, this year Indonesia's HDI increased from 66.53 in 2010 to 71.92 in 2019. During this period, Indonesia's HDI grew by an average of 0.87 percent per year and has increased from "moderate" to "high" levels since 2016. The COVID-19 pandemic has brought little change in the achievement of Indonesia's human development. HDI in 2020 was recorded at 71.94 or grew 0.03 percent, slowing down compared to the previous year's growth. With this achievement, the average HDI growth in 2010-2020 was 0.78 percent per year. Based on the Human Development Index / HDI, Indonesia is ranked 5th in ASEAN and 107th in the world out of 189 countries. Compared to neighboring countries in Southeast Asia, Indonesia is ranked fifth. Indonesia's HDI lost to Singapore, Brunei Darussalam, Malaysia and Thailand. With this data, the government must continue to strive to improve the quality of the education and health system so that the development of the country's human resources continues to improve, and Indonesia's welfare continues to be created optimally. Through the creation of social welfare, an individual in society can exert his potential and become a person who is able to function socially. As the Indonesian state law on social welfare follows: "Social Welfare is a condition for the fulfillment of the material, spiritual, and social needs of citizens in order to live a decent life and be able to develop themselves, so as to carry out their social functions". According to Midgley (in Adi, 2012), the state of well-being can be seen from three elements, namely: 1. The degree to which a social problem can be managed 2. To what extent the needs of the community can be met and 3. The level at which opportunities for self-development are provided or facilitated by the government. Social welfare includes two dimensions, namely: 1. what people get from their country (including programs, benefits, and services) and 2. how well the needs of the community are met (including social, economic, educational and health needs). Therefore, the meaning of social welfare does not only include conditions, but also includes development, activities and science. Social welfare is an organized system of various institutions and social welfare efforts designed to help individuals or groups achieve a more satisfactory standard of living and health.

In order to realize social welfare, it is necessary to have a social welfare enterprise. Social welfare enterprises are basically programs that are designed to answer problems, needs or aim to improve people's lives. The targets are not only individuals, but also include families, groups, and the wider community. Organizations that provide social services (social welfare enterprises) are often referred to as Human Service Organizations (HSO). According to Hasenfeld (2010) HSO has differences between other organizations, namely 1. HSO works directly with unique humans, in other words its raw material is directly managed by HSO, 2. HSO has a mandate to protect and promote welfare for its clients. Indonesia heritage foundation as an educational institution is a service organization for the community that aims to change or improve personal attributes of clients or also called people changing. Through this institution, students are expected to improve their abilities so that they can improve their skills in carrying out social functions in society. In its services, the school provides services both to students, students who have normal social functions, as well as to students who experience limitations so that they are hampered in developing their social functions in society. Indonesia Heritage Foundation seeks to directly address people as its clients and has an obligation to create its goals towards better change. Indonesia Heritage Foundation participates in pursuing social welfare in Indonesia by building quality human resources through education. Indonesia Heritage Foundation seeks to support the

development of human resources by building the character of these human resources. With human resources with character, other elements that are prerequisites for the formation of quality and adequate human resources, both technically and non-technically, will be more likely to be achieved optimally. Indonesia Heritage Foundation is a non-profit organization in June 2000. In the last 20 years, Indonesia Heritage Foundation has developed and run several programs including community-based character education programs that have been run in more than kindergartens, PAUD (Early Childhood Education) and RA: 3,800 schools & 7,600 teachers, elementary schools: 824 schools & 648 teachers, in locations especially in poor areas throughout Indonesia. The program was initially carried out at the kindergarten level, which eventually became a pilot project and was eventually developed as a pilot for a similar program. This program has been established since 19 years ago, since its establishment until now, this program has not conducted research related to evaluation in its implementation. From the description above, researchers are interested in evaluating community-based character education programs at the kindergarten level by emphasizing how the program runs.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This research is included in the evaluation research with a type of formative evaluation research with an emphasis on process studies. Referring to Patton (2002) process as a focus in evaluation has implications for the emphasis on seeing how the result or output is produced rather than just looking at the results alone, that is a process analysis with which a program produces results. The evaluation process in the formative realm develops descriptively and inductively. Referring to Herman (1987) that formative evaluation focuses on the following : 1. The formative evaluator will test the implementation of the program components carried out on site. 2. The evaluator will also test the progress of cognitive achievement, attitudinal, performance and or other impacts. The method used in this study is with a qualitative approach. Qualitative data provide depth and detail through direct citation and meticulous descriptions of program situations, events, people, interactions, and observed behaviors (Patton: 2002).

A research result is said to be valid when the quality of the data and information contained in the research can be trusted and accounted for. To improve the quality of research, in this study used data triangulation strategies. Krefting (1991) suggests that triangulation is a strategy to improve the quality of research. This study used data triangulation carried out by examining the results of interviews conducted with different sources. Furthermore, the data obtained are checked with other facts, namely with observations and other raw data. In addition to triangulating data sources, in this study theoretical triangulation was also carried out. In this study, theory triangulation was carried out by comparing and interpreting the results of analysis from research with related theories.

The study used a non-probability sample selection technique with purposive sampling type. A non-probability technique is defined as a technique that does not provide equal opportunities or opportunities for a population to be sampled so that it is very specific and certain in nature. While purposive sampling is defined as sampling that refers to the goals and needs of the researcher (Neum: 2013). In other words, the informant sought is the informant who is considered to have the information we need according to the purpose of the study so that everyone does not have the same opportunity to become an informant. Which consists of the Founder, Teachers, Principals, Parents, Program Staff and Alumni of the students.

This study used data collection techniques through interviews and observations, both of which are primary data. Meanwhile, secondary data collection is carried out through a review of literature related to research. Interviews can be conducted by face to face interviews with participants, either individually or through focus group interviews consisting of six to eight participants per group. Observation is a process of direct observation by recording the symptoms encountered. The types of observations carried out are observations of situations and non-participants (Creswell : 2016).

In this evaluation study, the evaluation model used refers to the model developed by Kusek and Rist (in Morra 2009: 109). The evaluation model developed consists of five components, namely as follows: 1. Input, which is the resources that enter into a program. 2. Activities, which are activities carried out in the implementation of the program. 3. Output, i.e. a measure generated as a result of an activity. 4. Outcomes,

which are changes in behavior resulting from the implementation of a program. 5. Impact, which is what is expected or will be achieved from the implementation of the program.

The logic model of this program is: Impact: Realizing the acceleration and expansion of the range of application of the PHBK model throughout Indonesia. Outcomes: Providing access to underprivileged communities to obtain high-quality education through the application of the Character-Based Holistic Education (PHBK) model. Ensuring the quality of education The high-standard PHBK model encourages the community and non-governmental institutions (individuals and companies) to play an active role in building community character. Output: Availability of access for underprivileged communities in obtaining education with the application of Character-Based Holistic Education (PHBK). The participants of the education can become human beings with character, intelligence and high thinking. The community plays a direct role in building a characterful educational participant. Activities: School establishment, PHBK Model Training, Inter-school Meetings, Monitoring. Inputs: Beneficiaries, Facilities, HR Management, HR Teachers, Funds and Networks.

III. RESEARCH RESULTS

In general, the community-based character education program carried out by Yayasan X seeks to provide access to underprivileged communities to obtain high-quality education through the application of the Character-Based Holistic Education (PHBK) model. As well as encouraging the community and non-governmental institutions (individuals and companies) to play an active role in building the character of the Indonesian people by supporting the implementation of the program.

Community-based education programs have several activities in their implementation. Program activities are obtained by translating the objectives of the program. Based on the training proposal made by Indonesia Heritage Foundation, the activities in the implementation of community-based education programs are as follows;

PHBK model training for teachers. Indonesia Heritage Foundation strives to provide ready-made materials to assist educators in implementing the character-based Holistic Education model on site. Teachers are given training before applying this learning model in schools. The purpose of this training is to motivate and shape teachers so that they can become friendly and loving teachers, motivate children, and are able to create a challenging and fun learning environment. There are 2 models of training implementation for teachers: Training located at the foundation for 10 days and on-site training that wants to adopt PHBK for 5 days (in-house training). The material provided by the training includes providing material with lecture methods, group discussions, practice and mentoring as well as observation and internships. The content of the material provided includes about; Insight into the Need for Character Education through KBK (Competency-Based Curriculum) and Permen (Ministry Regulation) 58 as well as the National Character and Culture Education program. Self-Concept (Motivational Training), Developmentally appropriate Practices (Proper and Fun Education), Effective Communication and Classroom Management How to Stream Character Education in the Classroom, Brain Based Learning and Teaching, Application of Brain Based Learning in Themes and sentra activities, Creativity in making Origami, Classroom Props and Displays, Character-Based Holistic Learning Practices, Singing and Movement, Body Sports and Storytelling Techniques, Evaluation System, Portfolio and Report Card. This training program is also integrated with practice in mentoring groups (in class-training) as well as internships to teach directly in schools that implement PHBK. Thus the teacher has real experience in implementing the program and together with the instructor can conduct an evaluation.

Application of the PHBK model. In this program, teachers can implement the PHBK model in schools or locations where each participant comes from. The participants are expected to be able to gradually and consistently use the PHBK model. The application of the PHBK model is contained in several points, including the Perception of Character Pillars with systematic character education for 15-20 minutes every morning. Integrating the process of character education in centers (sentra activities). A conducive school environment, teachers who have been educated with PHBK training will become teachers who are friendly, dedicated, and become facilitators who are loved and loved by children. Co-parenting by involving parents in the application of

character at home (parents are given specific instructions for applying each pillar characters, alongside with an evaluation sheet). Study time every Monday – Friday at 8.00 AM – 11.00 PM.

Meeting between school program implementers, Yayasan X as the program organizer tries to ensure that there is a network between schools in each region in Indonesia. In its implementation, the trainee teachers formed a communication forum throughout Indonesia. Especially for schools implementing the program spread across 34 provinces in Indonesia, meetings are held once a month. Meetings are usually held either in each city or province according to the agreement and meetings are usually held for approximately 1-6 hours.

Next is monitoring, all schools can be monitored for 6 months (if needed with sponsorship funds). However, the PHBK model itself has prepared instant modules and lesson plans that are so detailed (up to activities in the day and hour) that make it easier for teachers to implement them. So, if the monitoring /evaluation funds from the sponsor are not provided, hopefully that the learning process can take place successfully.

Program Implementation

Indonesia Heritage Foundation as an organization that provides social services or what is often referred to as human service organizations or HSO. With what is done, Yayasan X plays a role and is responsible for participating in pursuing social welfare in Indonesia, by building quality human resources through character education. Through community-based character education programs, Yayasan X tries to target the wider community. Through this community-based education, the community is involved from the beginning of the formation to the monitoring carried out together. Through the concept of community-based education, this program is a form of education managed by the community by utilizing existing facilities in the community and emphasizes the importance of community participation in every learning activity and aims to answer the needs of the community, especially in the field of human resources (HR).

Based on field findings, the implementation of this program begins with providing training on the concept of education and character through PHBK to teachers obtained from the surrounding community. Through this PHBK method, it is hoped that teachers can optimize the motor, art, cognitive, language, and character of existing students. This training actually applies to all teachers in schools. It's just that between one teacher and another the distance that is carried out is different, sometimes the number of days is different, this is because there is a compaction or different training system in each batch or session. In relation to the material provided in accordance with the attached provisions that the teaching staff get about; Insight into the Need for Character Education through KBK (Competency-Based Curriculum) and Ministry Regulation 58 as well as the National Character and Culture Education program. Self-Concept (Motivational Training), Developmentally Appropriate Practices (Appropriate and Fun Education), Effective Communication and Classroom Management How to Flow Character Education in the Classroom, Brain Based Learning and Teaching, Application of Brain Based Learning in Themes and sentra System, Creativity in making Origami, Class Props and Displays, Character-Based Holistic Learning Practices, Singing and Movement, Body Sports and Storytelling Techniques, Evaluation System, Portfolio and Report Card. However, the duration and compaction are adjusted to the type of training that the teacher attends.

Furthermore, the teachers carried out the PHBK model in the implementation of pillar streaming activities carried out every morning for 15-20 minutes. There are activities through knowing through storytelling and acting with role play, with affirmations through songs and singing. In applying the PHBK model, teachers have implemented centers well. This is in order to integrate the process of character education. The centers are Imagination, Design, Art creation, Exploration, Garden, Fish and livestock, Preparation, Faith and Devotion. This program actually seeks to involve parents in the application of character at home with informal parenting activities and in schools with picket activities. It also found activities related to empowerment where parents made efforts to empower the economy through selling. The implementation of this model implementation activity takes place every Monday to Friday starting from 08:00 AM to 11:00 PM.

This program actually also encourages teachers and several related stakeholders to communicate with each other through the forum provided. This also encourages the opening of networks between fellow education activists throughout Indonesia. One of the activities in this program is to hold meetings between implementing schools. This activity is also expected to be attended by all schools that join the program, but in its

implementation not all can participate in this activity. This is because many schools are not well recorded by their contact persons. In addition, the condition of school locations spread throughout Indonesia resulted in several locations not being accessed. In its implementation, Indonesia Heritage Foundation has a forum that is a gathering place for schools, but this has not made all schools that participate in the program can be joined properly. In the implementation, it found that related to the schedule and duration did not have certainty or a definite time.

The last activity is monitoring carried out by the foundation as the owner of the program. In fact, this monitoring is carried out by human resources from the foundation and is carried out once every 6 months. In the implementation of monitoring every 6 months, it is carried out only if the donor asks the foundation for monitoring. However, the foundation often monitors for an irregular period of time. In its implementation, it is known that the monitoring carried out is usually in the form of real time visits before the pandemic, and during the pandemic is usually monitoring and carried out online either using the zoom meeting application or whatsapp group. In addition, it is known that the foundation often monitors using an extension, namely the union of teachers who are members of this program. This is due to the small number of human resources of the foundation in charge of this program and in order to maximize the role of the forum or union.

IV. CONCLUSION

From this study, it was found that the community-based character education program carried out by Indonesia Heritage Foundation as a human service organization that focuses on character education in the development of human resources with character, intelligence and high mindedness. Through this program, Indonesia Heritage Foundation as a service organization for the community that aims to change or improve the personal attributes of clients or also called people changing which seeks to improve the ability of its beneficiaries so that they can improve skills in carrying out social functions in society.

In its implementation, this program has not run in accordance with the SOP or the initial setting up of the program. From the description of the analysis above, it can be seen that the point of training activities and school meetings of the program is still not as it should be. In the findings, it can be seen that there are 2 teachers who received training before teaching or implementing PHBK. There is 1 teacher participating in the training when it has been 2 weeks of teaching. This is because the training schedule is only available for 2 weeks after the teacher enters. So that teachers who took part in the training after 2 weeks of teaching had experienced confusion in terms of delivering the PHBK to students. The next activity that is still not appropriate is the meeting of all schools participating in the program. In its implementation, it can be seen that not all can participate in this activity, caused by poor databases and access to school locations spread throughout Indonesia. In addition, the place to gather for schools' members/participants, but this has not made all schools that participate in the program able to join properly. In the implementation, it was also found that related to the schedule and duration did not have certainty or a definite time. As for the implementation of the PHBK model and monitoring, it is already in accordance with the SOP. In the implementation, it can also be seen that community-based character education carried out by Indonesia Heritage Foundation, can be adopted or used as a similar educational model.

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